

Assessing the Persistence of Permanent Grassland in Slovenia Using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 Time Series

Tatjana Veljanovski^{1,*}, Matic Lubej², Ana Potočnik Buhvald³, Krištof Oštir³, Grega Milčinski²

¹ Institute of Anthropological and Spatial Studies, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts, Ljubljana, Slovenia, tatjana.veljanovski@zrc-sazu.si

² Sinergise Solutions, Ltd, Ljubljana, Slovenia, matic.lubej@sinergise.com, grega.milcinski@sinergise.com

³ Chair of Geoinformatics and Real Estate Cadastres, Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia, ana.potocnik-buhvald@fgg.uni-lj.si, kristof.ostir@fgg.uni-lj.si

* corresponding author

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Abstract: To understand the condition and stability of grassland ecosystems, information on grassland persistence is essential. This study aimed to quantify the persistence of permanent grassland in Slovenia using the grassland age metric and to identify related spatiotemporal patterns of conservation and change. We analysed changes in grassland maintenance using time series of Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 satellite imagery from 2000 to 2021. Using a machine learning-based Bare Soil Marker model, we identified disturbances to grassland greenness caused by exposed soil on grassland parcels. The results, presented as national statistics aggregated by administrative region, indicate that 98 % of Slovenia's permanent grasslands remained unchanged over the study period. However, substantial regional differences were observed, with losses of up to 5 % in some areas and below 0.3 % in others. These findings highlight the importance of information on grassland permanence for official national statistics and for stakeholders involved in nature conservation and land management.

Keywords: grassland age; grassland persistence indicator; bare soil detection; LightGMB classifier; satellite image time series.

1 Introduction

Information on grassland sustainability is vital for understanding the condition and stability of grassland ecosystems and for guiding conservation and management actions. It provides clear evidence of the long-term maintenance of grassland. Grassland persistence benefits plant species richness and resilience to disturbances such as climate variability. It is therefore also an indicator of the quality of biodiversity at both the landscape and ecosystem levels.

Permanent grasslands in Europe, defined as grasslands not used in crop rotation for at least five years, comprise more than a third of European agricultural land. However, a recent study by the European Environment Agency has revealed a net decline in grassland area (EEA 2021). Key threats to grassland ecosystems include changes in precipitation and temperature (Blair et al. 2014, Chang et al. 2021, Iepema et al. 2022), intensive management practices, and the conversion of grassland to annual crops (De Vroey et al. 2022). Ensuring the conservation of permanent grasslands aligns with the Common Agricultural Policy and biodiversity objectives. Accurate data on grasslands is therefore crucial for developing

effective agro-environmental indicators to support regional and global policy. Achieving this will require detailed characterisation of grassland types, assessment of grassland management strategies, productivity levels, and conservation value.

Few studies have investigated methods for assessing the age of grassland cover using multiple satellite images. Vannoppen et al. (2023) presented a framework for producing annual historical land cover maps for Flanders, Belgium, from 2005 to 2019, based on random forest classification of Landsat time series. In our study, the age of a grassland area was defined by the continuous presence of grass throughout the growing season (April–October) over 21 years.

Permanent grassland cannot be ploughed, used to grow crops, or used for the deposition of materials. If the uninterrupted presence of grass without disturbances is confirmed annually, statistical conclusions can be drawn about the observed grassland area. Therefore, the persistence of grassland cover provides insight into the conservation or degradation of grasslands, making it a valuable indicator of the long-term condition of grassland ecosystems. We demonstrate how historical Sentinel-2 and Landsat satellite image time series were used to evaluate the stability of grasslands in Slovenia (~3,500 km²). This national assessment is the first large-scale monitoring of grassland longevity in Slovenia. To the best of our knowledge, it is also the first such monitoring exercise in Europe.

The objective of the study was to determine the age of each permanent grassland parcel in Slovenia for a 21-year period using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 5/8 satellite data. We applied a Bare Soil Marker (BSM) model, based on a LightGMB classifier, to detect soil exposed due to ploughing or changes in grassland use. We adapted the BSM model, originally developed for Sentinel-2, and retrained it with the Landsat series to ensure comparability in bare soil maps. We summarised BS detections within each growing season and produced annual BS maps indicating bare soil presence at the pixel level. We then determined the continuity of each grassland pixel by counting the number of years without bare soil, and as a result, provided a grassland age map. The results, presented as national statistics aggregated by administrative region, illustrate the status, dynamics and trends of grassland permanence and change in Slovenia over the two decades.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study focuses on Slovenia, where grasslands and pasturelands cover 18% of the land area (17% are permanent grasslands) and represent 58% of the total agricultural area (MKGP 2023). These grasslands include extensive and intensive grassland, pastures, marshy meadows, and other types, and are mostly semi-natural. The high fragmentation of agricultural parcels means that ~5% cannot be monitored with Sentinel-2 and Landsat data (Potočnik Buhvald et al. 2022).

2.2 Datasets

The area of interest represented the entire permanent grassland area in Slovenia, extracted from the Land Parcel Information System (LPIS). The mask covers permanent grasslands class in 2021.

The bare soil collection for arable land in Slovenia was prepared as part of Area monitoring activities and includes up to 26,000 labelled Sentinel-2 image samples from 2019 (Sinergise 2022). This dataset contains the date of the satellite image and flags for bare soil events that support the machine learning BSM classifier.

We used data from Landsat 5, Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 optical satellites. Landsat 5 (period 2000-2011) and Landsat 8 (period 2013- 2021), both from NASA, provide a 30 m resolution and a 16-day repeat cycle. Sentinel-2 (period 2017-2021, with two S-2A and S-2B satellites in operation) provides enhanced imagery with 10 m resolution and a 5-day revisit time. The combined data from these satellites span more than 20 years, which is crucial to assess the age of grasslands.

The aggregation mask was used to calculate national statistics by defining the grassland area of interest for a given year. The mask covers permanent grasslands and enables selection of grassland areas to be aggregated to NUTS3, NUTS2 or other regions, and can therefore provide different statistical summaries.

2.3 Methodology

Atmospherically corrected Level 2A raster images were converted into EOPatches (EOPatch is a Python class data container for EO and non- EO data from the eo-learn package), each containing spectral bands, vegetation indices, quality flags and masks. The Sentinel Hub's pipeline provided s2cloudless cloud masks and probabilities for Sentinel-2 data (Sentinel Hub, 2018), while Landsat data contained Band Quality Assessment (BQA) for cloud detection. Sentinel-2 imagery was further refined with s2cloudless to filter clouds, shadows, haze, and anomalies and ensure the validity of the time series. Finally, the raster time series were transformed into data frames, where each row represents a pixel with observed spectral bands, vegetation indices, acquisition dates, and land use attributes.

2.3.1 Training and adapting the bare soil detection model

The Bare Soil Marker model can detect areas of bare soil

caused by ploughing, as well as areas of non-photosynthetic vegetation resulting from harvesting or desiccation (Sinergise 2022). It relies on four Sentinel-2 vegetation indices, NDVI, NBSI, NDVIRE3, and CLRe, to assign bare soil probabilities and classify observations above 0.8 (on a scale of 0 to 1) as bare soil. The model was pre-trained on labelled cropland and grassland data using a decision tree approach to minimize sensitivity to noisy labels and reduce overfitting (Sinergise 2022). Once the model is trained, it can classify all observations in the dataset as bare soils or non-bare soils.

The BSM model, originally trained using the 2019 Sentinel-2 labelled data, was adapted to account for the heterogeneous time series of Landsat 8 and Landsat 5. Separate BSM models were trained for each satellite source to ensure consistency.

For the Landsat 8 dataset, the original BSM model was re-trained with Landsat 8 data, retaining the 2019 Sentinel-2 reference dataset as a training dataset. Optimal spectral bands and indices were selected, followed by hyper-parameter optimization to fine-tune the model and minimize overfitting (Lubej 2023). Performance comparisons (ROC curve) of the Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 models are shown in Figure 1 (left). The application of a negative buffer (shrinking polygons by half a pixel) improved accuracy by reducing data mixing on borders of polygons.

Due to the lack of overlap between Landsat 5 (2000–2011) and Sentinel-2 (reference data 2019), a different training approach was required. We harmonised Landsat 5 with Landsat 8 using a linear regression method (Roy et al. 2016), transforming Landsat 5 bands into Landsat 8 spectral space. We then applied the Landsat 8 bare soil model to Landsat 5 data, omitting one band not covered by Landsat 5. After transformation, we retrained the Landsat 8 model with a subset of the Landsat 5 bands and achieved similar performance (Figure 1, right).

Using the BSM model applied to customised input data from various sensors, we could determine bare soil presence in a grassland for all available image dates.

Figure 1. Left: The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for the Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 models are shown for land parcels with (red and orange) and without a negative buffer (green and blue). Right: The performances of the Landsat 8 model with the original bands (green) and the Landsat 5 band subset (orange, blue) mostly overlap, indicating no significant effect from reducing the spectral information used.

2.3.2 Bare soil annual layers

Annual bare soil (BS) layers were created at the pixel level, requiring at least two consecutive BS observations per year for confirmation. Analysis of Sentinel-2 BS layers from 2017 to 2021 showed that BS is rare in permanent grasslands (covering less than a few percent of the area), while it occurs much more frequently on arable land, as expected. The consistency of BS detection between data sources shows strong agreement. Differences were observed for arable land, but these are not relevant to grassland age determination. Therefore, the condition proposed for permanent grasslands was optimised to ensure comparable performance across different satellite data sources.

2.3.3 Aggregations to NUTS regions

The aim of data aggregation was to provide statistics on a coarser scale for larger regions. We aggregated data at the NUTS2 and NUTS3 levels to provide regional statistics, using the majority function in Zonal Statistics tool in QGIS to determine the total area of bare soil presence on grassland per year.

3 Results

3.1 Annual maps of bare soil presence

Bare soil maps were generated for all years with available satellite data and compared. Figure 2 shows the most comparable year, 2019, using Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data, including close-up subsets. Sentinel-2 detected BS more frequently and over a larger total area than Landsat 8. These differences can be attributed to both sensor resolution and the adaptation of the BSM model to earlier Landsat imagery. Differences are more pronounced on arable land than on grasslands. Higher occurrences of BS (>10 counts) in grasslands mainly appear as isolated pixels along parcel boundaries adjacent to other land uses. Despite such pixel-level anomalies, BS detection is stable and consistent at the parcel level across all sensors and years. The average difference in BS detection for the period 2017-2021 between Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 is 0.16 % of the total grassland area.

3.2 Map of grassland age

The age of the grasslands was estimated using annual maps showing the presence of bare soil on the grasslands from 2021 to 2000, by counting the number of consecutive years without detected exposure to bare soil (Figure 3). In 2012, a data gap occurred between the decommissioning of Landsat 5 and the launch of Landsat 8, this was treated separately by replicating the results from 2011. The analysis revealed that 96 % of grassland areas (3,376 km²) have remained undisturbed for more than 20 years, while 2 % (69 km²) were identified as grassland younger than five years. Young grasslands are distributed throughout the country, with fewer in the northern mountain regions and more in the agricultural and drier regions of the south-west. The higher presence of young grasslands in agricultural areas aligns with management practices involving five-year crop rotation schemes, which allow temporary conversion of grasslands to croplands or fallow land. Overestimation of bare soils in drier regions and during dry periods can also contribute to apparent reductions in grassland age due to transient vegetation stress or soil exposure.

3.3 Statistics by the NUTS3 regions

The spatial summary of bare soil presence within grassland parcels was calculated at both NUTS3 (12 statistical regions) and NUTS2 (2 statistical regions) levels using zonal aggregation techniques. Grassland parcels where no bare soil was detected during the analysis period (2000–2021) were classified as old permanent grassland, comprising 96 % of the analysed area. The remaining parcels were assigned to five age classes: 0–4, 5–9, 10–14, 15–19, and ≥20 years. For each statistical region, the proportion of unmodified grassland (≥20 years old) is shown, together with pie charts illustrating the distribution of the other grassland age classes (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Maps of bare soil presence across crop fields and grasslands in Slovenia for the year 2019, derived from the Bare Soil Marker workflow using Sentinel-2 imagery (left) and harmonized Landsat 8 data (right).

Figure 3. Grassland age mapping in the Zgornja Poljskava area, Slovenia. Age values range from 0 (red), indicating recently established or frequently disturbed grasslands, to 21 (green), representing long-term stable grasslands with uninterrupted vegetative cover.

Figure 4. Aggregated grassland age statistics for Slovenia from 2000 to 2021 at the NUTS3 regional level. This representation highlights regional differences in grassland persistence (green) and turnover (red) across 12 statistical regions.

ecosystem at the national scale, while also revealing regional trends of grassland decline during the observation period 2000–2021. Overall, this study presents a practical approach to operationalise grassland persistence and conversion for ecosystem monitoring and the study of their dynamics and trends. This information can inform sustainable land use planning and support applications in ecosystem monitoring, conservation assessment, and policy-relevant reporting.

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4 Conclusions

The study demonstrates the potential of combining remote sensing and machine learning to assess the conservation status of permanent grasslands over an extended period. Using Sentinel-2, Landsat 8 and Landsat 5 time series in combination with the Bare Soil Marker algorithm, we estimated the persistence and age of grassland cover based on the absence of bare soil. The presence of bare soil served as a reliable indicator of grassland use change and enabled the distinction between permanent and non-permanent grassland, as well as the assessment of grassland cover longevity – from regional to parcel and even sub-parcel level. The results confirm that it is possible to detect bare soil consistently throughout the years and across multiple sensors. In Slovenia, 96 % of the observed grassland area maintains continuity in grassland cover, and 98 % meets the criteria for permanent grassland, highlighting the long-term stability of the grassland

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